

Questions

A poem of rhetorical, philosophical, and existential questions echoing through the corridors of epistemology

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Do I seek the questions or are the questions the seekers?

For there are many with no answers...

I can't really tell if they are valid, or am I delusional?

Where are we going?

Is it all a cycle, a short concert and we're the dancers?

Shall I seek the heavens for assistance?

But should I question the keepers of this mysterious universe?

Shall I question the masters?!

Are the questions met with proof, or am I up for a trial?

Can I be superstitious?

Are we arguing witches and necromancers?!

Is it a mere chaotic system? A random series of events?

Are we merely a school of sweepers?!

Are we made for a purpose?

Or are we time-limited freelancers?

Is this life a piece of a longer journey?

Or one hell of a green mile?

And am I the smart one for asking the questions?

Or am I the idiot for not knowing the answers?